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URBANIZATION AND AIR POLLUTIN : A CASE STUDY OF BAHADURGRAH CITY

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Abstract

Rapid Urbanization demands the growth of cities in the world and various problems associated with the urbanization process i.e, inadequate water supply, unsatisfactory health, poor sanitation conditions, atmospheric pollution, growth of urban slums and loss of agricultural land poses a formidable challenge in many developing countries. The process of urbanization deals with the migration of people from primary sector to the tertiary sector. The process of urbanization is increasing in Bahadurgrah city with rapid rate and the city is sprawled towards its periphery. The main objective of this paper is to discuss the positive population of city and also see the negative impact these processes on the environment of Bahadurgrah. This paper is an attempt which are given in the paper in detail.

Key words: Urbanization, Environmental and Sprawl.

Introduction:

The process of urbanization is rapid all around the world. The facilities like education, healthcare system, employment, civic facilities, transportation, industrialization and social welfare are the reason attracting the people to urban area from the rural areas. High level of migration in Bahadurgrah city enhances the urbanization and this pulled migration stream is mainly from the inner districts of the Haryana State and from other States such as U.P Bihar and Rajasthan. With this migration stream there is a rapid increase in population and these city dwellers give birth to the development of slums. Environment degradation has become a major problem in Bahadurgrah city. Ecological degradation simply refers to the degrading for the ecological relationship between the living organisms and their environment by the humans and their activities. Ecological degradation mainly prevails in the industrial cities like Delhi, Mumbai, Kolkata etc. Before some time urbanization and industrialization become very fast in Bahadurgrah city. But conversely, growth of slums around industries, atmospheric pollution and the loss of valuable agricultural land due to urban sprawl prevail as chronic problems.

Study area:

Bahadurgrah city is an important industrial center of Jhajjar district of Haryana State. As per 2011 census 1,70,426 people in 31 municipal wards and spreads over an area of about 29 Sq. K.m. The population density of city is 5,7,47 person per Sq. K.m. The city lives between 28°41'N to 28°68' N latitudes and 76°55' E to 76°92' E longitudes. It has an average elevation of 207 meter from sea level. It is located at distance of 45 k.m from Rohtak, 35 kilometer from Jhajjar, situated 28 kilometer West of Delhi on Delhi Rohtak national Highway No-10. Bahadurgrah city is one of the fastest developing cities in the NCR region.

Objectives of the study:

1. To analyze the trends of urbanization in the Bahadurgrah city.
2. To explain the spatial growth of the city.
3. To identify the prominent types of environmental degradation included by the process of urbanization

Data base:

This paper based on both primary and secondary data. Date on population are based on the census of India and Statistical Abstract of Haryana from 1971 to 2011 as well as ,other information have been collected from the Haryana Pollution Board, Municipal Corporation of Bahadurgrah and some of the information are collected from the internet websites of Bahadurgrah.

Population growth:

Bahadurgrah was a small town in pre-independence period, that is , before 1947. The population of Bahadurgrah city in 1971 was 25,812 person and reached up to 1,70,426 persons in 2011. The city population indicates that during the decades of 1971-1981, it registered a decadal growth rate of 72.29 per cent.

Table-1

Population Growth of Bahadurgrah city: 1971 to 2011

Years	Population	Decadal variation in Population

1971	25,812	72.29
1981	37,488	45.23
1991	56,524	50.78
2001	1,19,846	112.03
2011	1,70,426	42.20

Source: Census of India 1971 to 2011

However, during period of 1991, the growth rate came down to 50.78 per cent because of normalized social and economic condition. During the period of 1991 to 2011 the growth in population touched 112.03 per cent due to industrialization and migration from other sates. In 2011 the population of Bahadurgarh reached up to 1,70,246 persons and the decadal per cent variation decreased which was 42.20 per cent in 2001d-2011 as shown in Table-1.

Spatial growth:

The total area of Bahadurgarh city was 2.59 Sq. Kilometer in 1971 and there was a tremendous increase in the area of Bahadurgarh it reached up to 9 Sq. Kilometer in 1981. This increase in area was due to the reason that the development activities started taking place in Bahadurgarh city or on its periphery.

Table-2

Population Density of Bahadurgarh city: 1971 to 2011

Year	Area(In Sq.k.m)	Persons	Persons per Sq.K.m
1971	2.59	25,812	9966
1981	9.0	37,488	4165
1991	9.0	56,524	6280
2001	29.65	1,19,846	4042
2011	29.65	1,70,426	5747

Source: Census of India 1971 to 2011

In 1991 the total area was 9.0 Sq. Kilometer in 2001 and remained the same in the decade up to 2011 as shown in Table-2. From 1971 to 2011 there was an increase of 27.06 Sq. Kilometer area in Bahadurgarh city and this increase in the area of Bahadurgarh city due to the development in industrial sector.

Air Pollution in Bahadurgarh City:

Air pollution is caused by the existence of large number of industrial units and had adverse impact on the air quality of Bahadurgarh city. In Bahadurgarh the major source of air pollution are the exhaust from automobiles on the roads from factories and dust suspension. Air pollution is an emerging problem that is disturbing our ecological system and we can say that the air pollution is affecting the relationship between the organisms and their environment. Air pollution is defined as the disequilibrium of the air caused due to introduction of foreign elements from natural as become injurious to biological communities in general and human community in particular. Air pollutants are added in the atmosphere from variety of sources that change the composition of air and effect of the biotic environment. Pollutants can be classified as either primary and secondary. Usually, primary pollutants are substances directly from a process. Such as ash from volcanic eruption or sulphur dioxides released from factories. The criteria pollutants measured are Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM), Respirable Suspended Monoxide (CO) etc. The pollutants coming out of natural sources are generally absorbed by the natural environment and no pollution problem arises by man-made pollutants being concentrated in certain parts of the atmosphere pollute the air. The quality of air that we breathe affects our health and quality of life. It can also have major impact on the ecosystem. The quality of air in Bahadurgarh city has declined due to air has declined due to air pollution.

Table-3

Air Quality in Sample Areas, 2011

Air Quality	Response in per cent		
Deterioration	Name of Localities		
	Kabir Basti	Chottu Ram Nagar	Vivekanand Nagar
Yes	86.7	83.3	80.0
No	3.3	6.7	6.3
Can't say	10.0	10.0	13.3

Source: Primary survey, 2011

In locality wise primary survey most of respondents from Kabir Basti, Chottu Ram Nagar and Vivekanand Nagar that air quality in their localities has been deteriorated due to poisonous emission from industrial units. In Kabir Basti, Chottu Ram Nagar and Vivekanand Nagar 86.7%, 83.3% and 80% respondents said air quality decline, 3.3%, 6.7% and 13.3% respondents respectively said air quality not declined and 10% respondents from both Kabir Basti, Chottu Ram Nagar and 13.3% respondent from Vivekanand Nagar were unaware about this.

Table-4

Air pollution load in Bahadurgarh city-2010

Name of Industrial Sector/ Units	Pollution Load (Kg/ day)					
	SPM	In Percent	SO ₂	In Percent	NO _x	In Percent
Textile Fabric Dying & Coating	263.3	40.6	11.1	20.6	2.7	13.2
Footwear	157.7	24.3	28.8	53.4	13.7	67.2
Pack ling, Electroplating & Engineering	72.2	11.2	6.6	12.2	2.1	10.3
Sanitary, Tiles, Crokery & Glass	58.1	8.9	0.5	0.9	-	-
Tyre Manufacturing	39.1	6.0	1.2	2.2	0.9	4.4
Chemicals	25.7	3.9	3.1	5.8	0.6	2.9
Recycling of Used oil	10.7	1.6	2.2	4.2	0.4	2.0
Others	22.4	3.5	0.4	0.7	-	-
Total	649.1	100.0	53.9	100	20.4	100

Source: Haryana State Pollution Control Board, Bahadurgarh, 2010

Table No-4 shows that the air pollution load from different industrial units in Bahadurgarh city, 2010. Haryana State Pollution Control Board has been monitoring the status of Air pollution load and their sources of emission by collecting and testing samples. There are 82 industrial units in Bahadurgarh that generates air pollution by emitting harmful gases. Out of these air-polluting unit 70 industrial units are situated in Modern Industrial Estate (MIE) I and ii Bahadurgarh city. The main Industrial sectors, which generate air pollution in city, are Textile Dyeing and Coating units, Footwear Manufacturing units, Chemical Manufacturing units, Sanitary, Tiles, Glass and Crokery Manufacturing units, Tyre Manufacturing units and Pickling, Electroplating and Engineering units. The industry wise emission of air pollution load in Bahadurgarh 2010 from different industrial unit by observing emission of SPM, SO₂ and NO_x. The total emission of SPM, SO₂ and NO_x from industrial units in Bahadurgarh city was 649.1

kg/day and 20.4 kg/day respectively in 2010. The major industrial sector, which emit SPM are Textile Fabric Dying and Coating units i.e 40.6 of total air pollution and followed by Footwear Manufacturing units(24.3%), units(8.9%), Tyre Manufacturing units(60%) , Chemicals units(39%), Recycling used oil units(1.6) and other including food, plywood, Pesticide Formulation units(3.5%). In case of SO₂ the main emitting industrial units are Footwear Manufacturing units i.e 53.4% of total emission followed by Textile Fabric Dying and Coating units(20.6%), Pickling, Electroplating and Engineering units(12.2%), Chemical units(5.8%), Recycling of used oil units(4.2%), Tyre Manufacturing(2.2%) and other industrial units(0.7%). The NO_x is mostly emitted by Footwear Manufacturing industry i.e 67.2% of total emission followed by Textile Fabric Dying and Coating units(13.2%), Pickling, and Recycling of used oil(2.0%) in Table-4.

In primary survey more than 80% responded that industrialization is the main problem of environmental pollution in the city. The pollution load generated by industrial units in the city is increasing day by day at an alarming rate. Water pollution in Bahadurgarh city is continuously deteriorating as the effluents of Industrial units and local bodies discharging untreated in to the Mungespur-West Zua drain. The ground water of adjacent areas of this drain is also contaminated. The ambient air quality of Bahadurgarh is also deteriorating. The emission of polluted gases in Environment is increasing due to growth of tertiary activities.

Thus, there is an urgent need for solving industrial pollution problems by adopting a balance approach between Industrial development and Environment management in Bahadurgarh city.

Conclusion:

With the march of time the area growth of Bahadurgarh is rapid enough and from 1971 to 2011, in the span of forty years, there is an increase 27.06% Sq. Kilometer. Besides, there was an increase of 1,44,614 persons in urban population from 1971 to 2011. This high urban population and areal growth in Bahadurgarh city is mainly due to the establishment of industrial sector, rural to urban migration and development in Transportation and communication. Urbanization and industrialization are very rapid rate. When the people start migrating from rural towards the urban areas change in various respects such as poor sanitary conditions, contamination of social, water and air solid waste lying on the road sides in the city. Man is the real culprit for all the evils of today environment problem and most of these problem arise due to the wrong usage of science and technology for the advancement of human beings. Besides, the Urbanization process of Bahadurgarh city is taking place at a rapid rate with an unplanned and unchecked way. The city extended or sprawled towards the periphery of Bahadurgarh with the loss of valuable agricultural land around the city.

Bahadurgarh city suffered from the problem of environment degradation. Lack of housing, drinking water, traffic problems and growth of slums in Bahadurgarh city are notorious. With the land prices soaring sky high the area of Bahadurgarh city sprawled towards the fringe of the city. Therefore, there is a need to tackle these problems and to identify the actions to be taken in the field of environmental and urban planning and proper planning should be based on the ecological attributes.

Suggestions:

1. There is an urgent need to check and identify the problem of Bahadurgarh city and addressing these problems through proper planing and implementing them rationally. Eco-friendly approach should be applied to make friendly relationship between man and environment.
2. For improving the quality of environmental education a compulsory learning at the school and college levels.

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